

NOTES

Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes of Some Tridentate Dibasic Schiff Bases of ONO Donor Type

REBATI C. DAS*, MIHIR K. MISRA

and

PRAKASH N. BOHIDAR

Department of Chemistry, University College of Engineering,
Burla-768 018

Manuscript received 24 August 1981, revised 22 September
1982, accepted 28 January 1983

OXOVANADIUM(IV) complexes exhibit various interesting coordination features like bridged and chained structures, uncommon subnormal magnetic moments^{1,2}, etc. In continuation of our work on complexes of tridentate Schiff bases of ONO donor type containing amino acids³⁻⁶, we report here some oxovanadium complexes of Schiff base ligands obtained by condensing salicylaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone or acetylacetone with glycine, anthranilic acid or β -alanine.

The complexes were prepared following the procedure of Theriot *et al*² in 70-80% yield. The compounds have low solubility in methanol and more so in dehydrated methanol. Molar conductivities in dilute methanolic solution ($\sim 10^{-3}$ M) qualitatively show the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The analytical data show them to be of 1 : 1 type in metal ligand ratio.

Infrared spectra of the compounds show modified ligand absorption bands. A shift of $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ bands by 40-100 cm^{-1} to lower frequency in the 3500 cm^{-1} region and the appearance of bands in the region ~ 860 cm^{-1} indicate^{6,7} coordinated water molecules. This is further supported by the absence of any loss of water at 100°.

The $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ vibrations occur within 1580-1605 cm^{-1} , either separately or along with those of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$, and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ vibrations occur at 1440 cm^{-1} . The resulting difference ($\Delta\nu$) of ~ 150 cm^{-1} is prescribed for monodentate carboxylates⁸⁻¹⁰. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ phenolic vibration in both the ligands derived from salicylaldehyde and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone occurs at ~ 1510 cm^{-1} . This vibration in the complexes of the former is 10-15 cm^{-1} higher than the corresponding ligands. But this shift is of the order of 35 cm^{-1} in the complexes of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives. Both the positions of $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ bands of the complexes as well as the shift ($\Delta\nu$) may be attributed to monodentate phenolic oxygen in the former compounds and bridged oxygen in the latter compounds¹¹⁻¹³. The

corresponding $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ vibration in complexes derived from acetylacetoneimino acids appear at ~ 1520 cm^{-1} with that of their ligands at ~ 1550 cm^{-1} indicating the monodentate nature of the corresponding oxygen atom⁸. The $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibrations in the present complexes occur between 933-995 cm^{-1} which is the normal range of absorption of majority of oxovanadium(IV) complexes of non-chained structure^{14,15}.

Electronic spectra of the complexes have been taken from nujol and methanol. Besides bands of charge transfer origin^{1,4,16} at $\sim 25,000$, $\sim 32,000$, $\sim 36,000$ and $\sim 40,000$ cm^{-1} , the ligand field absorptions occur mainly at $\sim 12,000$, $\sim 17,000$ and $\sim 23,000$ cm^{-1} from $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{yz}$, d_{zx} ; $\rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $\rightarrow d_{z^2}$ transitions, respectively. The band positions in methanol are slightly different from those in nujol and this may be due to slight participation of the solvent in the coordination sphere in the former case. The ν_2 bands in the complexes derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acids in general occur at lower frequencies (16,000-16,200 cm^{-1}) compared to those of other complexes (16,500-17,200 cm^{-1}). This shift to lower frequency may be due to hexacoordination^{1,17-19} in the former compounds. Donor property of *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acids is more than that of the other ligands described in the paper. A further supporting evidence of hexacoordination in complexes derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acids comes from the fact that although salicylideneamino acid complexes absorb (due to ν_2 band) at $\sim 17,200$ cm^{-1} , solution in pyridine shifts the band to $\sim 15,900$ cm^{-1} —a position where the bands due to *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acid complexes occur. It may be that the five-coordinated complexes of salicylideneamino acids are changed to distorted octahedral in strong donor solvents like pyridine due to solvent participation. The electronic spectra therefore indicate five-coordinated square pyramidal geometry for all complexes except those derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acids which possibly have distorted octahedral structure.

The octahedral geometry in the latter can only be achieved by dimerisation. This is consistent with the observed bridging through phenolic oxygen atom in the infrared spectra of *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acid complexes. Such a $\text{O}=\text{V} \text{ O} \text{ V}=\text{O}$ bridging is expected to affect the magnetic moment. In support of the above, normal magnetic moment of ~ 1.85 B.M. is observed in rest of the complexes as expected for spin-free d^1 configuration^{20,21}, but those derived from *o*-hydroxyacetophenoneimino acids have lower magnetic moment (~ 1.45 B.M. due to magnetic quenching).

TABLE 1—COLOUR, ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF OXOVANADIUM(IV) COMPLEXES OF THE SCHIFF BASES

Compounds ^a	Colour	Decomp. point (°C)	Analysis %			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			V	N	H ₂ O	
VOSg H ₂ O	Blue	210	19.3 (19.47) ^b	5.2 (5.35)	6.6 (6.87)	1.79
VOSa H ₂ O	Greyish green	225	16.5 (16.38)	4.2 (4.49)	5.5 (5.77)	1.96
VOSal H ₂ O	Light green	245	18.0 (18.48)	4.9 (5.07)	6.5 (6.53)	1.86
VOHg H ₂ O	Blue	220	18.4 (18.48)	4.7 (5.07)	6.2 (6.53)	1.45
VOHa H ₂ O	Deep blue	235	14.8 (15.08)	4.1 (4.14)	5.2 (5.32)	1.45
VOHal H ₂ O	Light blue	255	17.4 (17.69)	4.7 (4.83)	6.0 (6.21)	1.49
VOAg H ₂ O	Bluish green	270	21.3 (21.26)	5.6 (5.83)	7.5 (7.50)	1.77
VOAa H ₂ O	Brown	280	16.6 (16.89)	4.5 (4.63)	5.8 (5.96)	1.88
VOAal H ₂ O	Blue	250	19.8 (20.18)	5.3 (5.51)	7.0 (7.09)	1.83

a. S, H and A stand for salicylidene, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and acetylacetonate moiety, respectively and g, a and al stand for glycine, anthranilic acid and β -alanine moiety, respectively of the corresponding Schiff bases.

b. Values in the parentheses are theoretical values.

References

- M. TEOTIA, J. N. GURTU and V. B. RANA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1980, **19A**, 133.
- L. J. THERIOT, G. O. CARLISLE and H. J. HU, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 3303.
- R. C. DAS, M. K. MISRA and S. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1978, **16A**, 170.
- R. C. DAS, M. K. MISRA and S. K. MOHANTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 667.
- R. C. DAS, M. K. MISRA and S. K. MOHANTY, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20A**, 528.
- R. C. DAS, M. K. MISRA and S. K. MOHANTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (communicated).
- J. FUJITA, A. E. MARTELL and K. NAKAMOTO, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 324, 331.
- K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1966.
- N. F. CURTIS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1579.
- K. DEY and K. C. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 66.
- M. KATO, K. IMAI, Y. MUTO, T. TOKII and H. B. JONASSEN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, **35**, 109.
- G. E. BATLEY and D. P. GRADDON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 877, 885.
- S. J. GRUBER, C. M. HARRIS and E. SINN, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1805.
- J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **65**, 153; *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 293.
- A. VAN DEN BERGEN, K. S. MURRAY, B. O. WEST and A. N. BUCKLEY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 2051.
- S. K. MOHANTY, Ph. D. Thesis, Sambalpur University, 1979.
- M. J. MCCORMICK, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1865.
- S. YAMADA and Y. KOGA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1969, **42**, 142.
- M. M. PATEL, M. R. PATEL, M. N. PATEL and R. P. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1981, **20A**, 623.
- A. SVAMAI and L. J. THERIOT, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 21.
- M. KATO, Y. MUTO, H. B. JONASSEN, K. IMAI and A. HARANO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, **41**, 1864.

Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Cobalt(II) and Iron(II) with Schiff's Bases Derived from 2-Pyrrolidone and Aromatic Amines

(MRS.) P. R. SHUKLA and JAYANT BHARGAVA

Department of Chemistry, University of Lucknow,
Lucknow-226 007

and

GOPAL NARAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Saugar, Saugar-470 003

Manuscript received 28 July 1981, revised 19 October 1982,
accepted 28 January 1983

CONDENSATION of 2-pyrrolidone with aromatic amines produces Schiff's bases with the following structure :

X = H ; *o*-, *m*- or *p*-CH₃

These are expected to act as bidentate ligands with the possibilities of donation from the NH and azomethine groups. Although a large number of Schiff's base complexes are reported, these ligands have not been studied till now. The present paper records the synthesis and characterisation of some complexes of these with copper(II), nickel(II), cobalt(II) and iron(II).

The Schiff's bases were obtained *in situ* by refluxing 2-pyrrolidone (1.0 mole) with an aromatic amine (1.0 mole), such as aniline, *o*-, *m*- or *p*-toluidine, in methanol for 6 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, a calculated amount of solid metal(II) sulphate in finely powdered form was added and was refluxed again. The reaction was stopped after 10 hr and the solid complexes which are blue, yellow, violet, pink or brown in colour were filtered and dried. These could not be recrystallised due to their insolubility in common solvents but were washed repeatedly with methanol for purification.

On the basis of elemental analysis the formulae of the complexes are $\text{MSO}_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{A}$, where M = Cu(II) or Ni(II) and $\text{MSO}_4 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4 \cdot \text{A}$, where M = Co(II) or Fe(II). The complexes, though insoluble in water, methanol and dimethylformamide, are soluble enough in nitrobenzene with the molar conductance values ($10^{-3} M$) in the range 20-26 mhos, suggesting that the anion is not coordinated. The molecular formulae of the complexes are thus truly represented as $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4\text{A}]\text{SO}_4$ and hence only one molecule of ligand along with two or four molecules of water are coordinated to metal(II) ions. The Cu(II) or Ni(II) complexes are thus tetra and Co(II) or Fe(II) complexes are hexacoordinated in nature.

The evidence for coordination of ligands is obtained by ir spectra. All the complexes exhibit